

Numerical observations on extremal Fourier coefficients of the Syracuse random variable

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Abstract

For the Syracuse random variable $\text{Syrac}(\mathbb{Z}/3^n\mathbb{Z})$ introduced by Tao [1], we report numerical computations of its characteristic function for $1 \leq n \leq 21$, covering supports of size up to $3^{21} \approx 1.05 \times 10^{10}$. Writing $\psi_n(k) := \mathbb{E} e^{-2\pi i 2^k \text{Syrac}/3^n}$ and $k^*(n) := \arg \max_k |\psi_n(k)|$ in a canonical fundamental domain, we observe that $k^*(n)$ exhibits an approximately linear drift with slope near $4/3$. The simple closed-form predictor $\lfloor 4(n-1)/3 \rfloor$ matches $k^*(n)$ for $n \in \{4, 5, \dots, 17\}$ and for $n = 19$, but fails at $n \in \{18, 20, 21\}$, with $k^*(n) - \lfloor 4(n-1)/3 \rfloor$ equal to $+1$, $+1$, and $+2$ respectively. The ratio $k^*(21)/21$ equals $4/3$ exactly. The interval slope $(k^*(21) - k^*(4))/17 = 24/17 \approx 1.412$ slightly exceeds $4/3$ because of the endpoint deviation at $n = 21$. We pose the asymptotic behaviour of $k^*(n)$ as a numerical open question.

1 Introduction

The Collatz conjecture asks whether iterating the map $\text{Col}(N) = N/2$ if N is even and $3N+1$ if N is odd, starting from any positive integer N , eventually reaches 1. In a major breakthrough, Tao [1] established that “almost all” Collatz orbits (in the logarithmic density sense) attain almost bounded values. The technical core of [1] is a fine-scale equidistribution analysis of an associated probabilistic object, the *Syracuse random variable*, defined as follows.

Definition 1 ([1, Definition 1.7, (1.21)]). For each $n \geq 1$, the Syracuse random variable $\text{Syrac}(\mathbb{Z}/3^n\mathbb{Z})$ on the cyclic group $\mathbb{Z}/3^n\mathbb{Z}$ is defined by

$$\text{Syrac}(\mathbb{Z}/3^n\mathbb{Z}) \equiv \sum_{m=1}^n 3^{m-1} \cdot 2^{-a_{[1,m]}} \pmod{3^n}, \quad (1)$$

where $a_{[1,m]} := a_1 + \dots + a_m$ and the a_j are i.i.d. copies of $\mathbf{Geom}(2)$, i.e., $\mathbb{P}(a_j = k) = 2^{-k}$ for $k \geq 1$.

A central technical estimate in [1] is the following super-polynomial decay of the characteristic function:

Proposition 2 ([1, Proposition 1.17]). *Let $n \geq 1$ and $\xi \in \mathbb{Z}/3^n\mathbb{Z}$ not divisible by 3. Then for any fixed $A > 0$,*

$$\left| \mathbb{E} e^{-2\pi i \xi \text{Syrac}(\mathbb{Z}/3^n\mathbb{Z})/3^n} \right| \ll_A n^{-A}. \quad (2)$$

This bound is established uniformly over ξ but does not, on its face, identify which ξ come closest to realising the bottleneck. The present paper records numerical observations on this question, drawn from full-domain numerical computation of ψ_n for $n \leq 21$.

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1.1 Notation

We write $\widehat{\text{Syrac}}_n(\xi) := \mathbb{E} e^{-2\pi i \xi \text{Syrac}(\mathbb{Z}/3^n\mathbb{Z})/3^n}$ for the characteristic function. Since 2 is a primitive root modulo 3^n for every $n \geq 1$ (a classical result), every $\xi \in (\mathbb{Z}/3^n\mathbb{Z})^*$ can be written uniquely as $\xi = 2^k \pmod{3^n}$ for some $k \in \{0, 1, \dots, 2 \cdot 3^{n-1} - 1\}$. Throughout the paper we therefore work with the dual-side function

$$\psi_n(k) := \widehat{\text{Syrac}}_n(2^k \pmod{3^n}), \quad (3)$$

which is periodic in k with period $2 \cdot 3^{n-1}$.

Since Syrac is integer-valued, its characteristic function satisfies

$$\widehat{\text{Syrac}}_n(-\xi) = \overline{\widehat{\text{Syrac}}_n(\xi)},$$

where $\bar{\cdot}$ denotes complex conjugation. In particular, $|\widehat{\text{Syrac}}_n(\cdot)|$ is invariant under $\xi \mapsto -\xi$. Using the classical fact

$$2^{3^{n-1}} \equiv -1 \pmod{3^n},$$

we have

$$-2^k \equiv 2^{k+3^{n-1}} \pmod{3^n},$$

and hence

$$\psi_n(k + 3^{n-1}) = \widehat{\text{Syrac}}_n(-2^k) = \overline{\psi_n(k)}.$$

Thus

$$|\psi_n(k + 3^{n-1})| = |\psi_n(k)|.$$

We use this symmetry to reduce the search to representatives $0 \leq k < 3^{n-1}$, and take $k^*(n)$ to be the smallest nonnegative representative on which $|\psi_n|$ attains its maximum.

2 Numerical observations

For each n in $1 \leq n \leq 21$, we compute ψ_n on its full domain in IEEE 754 double-precision complex arithmetic and record the location of the maximum modulus. The data are summarised in Table 1 and the underlying JSON file is included in the accompanying repository [3].

In Table 1, $g_n := M_n^2 - |\psi_n(k_2^*)|^2$ where k_2^* is the location of the second-largest value of $|\psi_n|^2$ over the canonical fundamental domain. The ratio g_n/M_n^2 measures how decisively $k^*(n)$ wins over the next candidate.

Observation 3 (Partial agreement with the floor formula). For $n \in \{4, 5, \dots, 17\}$ and for $n = 19$, $k^*(n)$ agrees with $\lfloor 4(n-1)/3 \rfloor$. The first deviation from the formula occurs at $n = 18$, where $k^*(18) = 23$ and $\lfloor 4 \cdot 17/3 \rfloor = 22$. Further deviations occur at $n = 20$ ($k^*(20) = 26$ versus 25) and at $n = 21$ ($k^*(21) = 28$ versus 26). Together with the small- n values $n = 2, 3$ (which lie outside the long agreement window), the set of n in $2 \leq n \leq 21$ for which $k^*(n) \neq \lfloor 4(n-1)/3 \rfloor$ is $\{2, 3, 18, 20, 21\}$. The floor formula thus describes $k^*(n)$ exactly on a long initial segment but is not a uniform identity in the present range.

Observation 4 (Slope near 4/3). At $n = 21$,

$$\frac{k^*(21)}{21} = \frac{28}{21} = \frac{4}{3} \quad \text{exactly.}$$

More generally, $k^*(n)/n$ over $4 \leq n \leq 21$ lies in the interval $[1.333, 1.400]$ and is consistent with an approximately linear growth of slope near 4/3. The interval slope

$$\frac{k^*(21) - k^*(4)}{21 - 4} = \frac{28 - 4}{17} = \frac{24}{17} \approx 1.4118$$

slightly exceeds 4/3, the excess being a direct consequence of the endpoint deviation $k^*(21) - \lfloor 4(21-1)/3 \rfloor = 2$. (The interior deviations at $n = 18, 20$ do not affect the interval slope directly.)

Table 1: Numerical values of $M_n := \max_k |\psi_n(k)|$, the canonical maximiser $k^*(n)$, the floor formula prediction $\lfloor 4(n-1)/3 \rfloor$, and the relative gap to the second-largest value $|\psi_n|^2$.

n	M_n	$k^*(n)$	$\lfloor 4(n-1)/3 \rfloor$	g_n/M_n^2
1	5.77350×10^{-1}	0	0	—
2	3.77924×10^{-1}	2	1	6.54×10^{-1}
3	2.52237×10^{-1}	3	2	4.06×10^{-1}
4	1.76999×10^{-1}	4	4	4.21×10^{-1}
5	1.29274×10^{-1}	5	5	3.94×10^{-1}
6	9.61064×10^{-2}	6	6	1.06×10^{-1}
7	7.58700×10^{-2}	8	8	1.05×10^{-1}
8	6.08907×10^{-2}	9	9	2.20×10^{-1}
9	4.80262×10^{-2}	10	10	1.19×10^{-1}
10	3.82783×10^{-2}	12	12	2.75×10^{-2}
11	3.19442×10^{-2}	13	13	1.33×10^{-1}
12	2.64582×10^{-2}	14	14	1.11×10^{-1}
13	2.20524×10^{-2}	16	16	2.52×10^{-2}
14	1.91280×10^{-2}	17	17	1.39×10^{-1}
15	1.62845×10^{-2}	18	18	1.36×10^{-2}
16	1.44095×10^{-2}	20	20	1.09×10^{-1}
17	1.25107×10^{-2}	21	21	2.27×10^{-2}
18	1.11873×10^{-2}	23	22	1.03×10^{-1}
19	9.81571×10^{-3}	24	24	9.42×10^{-3}
20	8.88459×10^{-3}	26	25	1.10×10^{-1}
21	7.87213×10^{-3}	28	26	1.15×10^{-2}

Remark 5 (Finite-range decay fit). Over the finite range $9 \leq n \leq 21$, a power-law fit $M_n \sim Cn^{-A}$ (least squares in $\log M_n$ versus $\log n$) yields $A \approx 2.10$. This is a finite-size observation only and should not be interpreted as an asymptotic claim. Tao’s Proposition 2 gives super-polynomial decay, namely $M_n \ll_A n^{-A}$ for every fixed $A > 0$; if one defines an effective exponent over finite windows, Tao’s result is compatible with such exponents increasing with n . The present data do not determine that behaviour.

Remark 6 (On the small-gap deviations). The deviations at $n = 18, 20, 21$ correlate with relatively small values of g_n/M_n^2 : at $n = 18$ the ratio is ≈ 0.103 , at $n = 20$ it is ≈ 0.110 , and at $n = 21$ it is the smallest among $n \geq 13$, namely ≈ 0.012 . By contrast, at $n = 19$ where the floor formula is exact, the ratio is ≈ 0.0094 , which is smaller still. We do not draw structural conclusions from these correlations on the basis of 19 data points alone.

Remark 7 (Tao’s exponential-decay conjecture). Tao remarks in [1, Remark 1.15] that the bound in his Proposition 1.17 should plausibly be improvable to $O(\exp(-cn))$ for some absolute $c > 0$. Our data in the range $n \leq 21$ are best fit by a polynomial form $M_n \sim Cn^{-2.1}$; an exponential fit over $9 \leq n \leq 21$ has roughly 20 times larger sum-of-squared-residual in $\log M_n$. This is fully consistent with Proposition 2 but suggests that any transition to exponential decay, if it exists, must occur at scales beyond the present range.

3 Method

The Syracuse random variable admits the explicit recursion of Tao [1, Lemma 1.12]. Writing $P_n(x) := \mathbb{P}(\text{Syrac}(\mathbb{Z}/3^n\mathbb{Z}) = x)$, we have

$$\text{Syrac}(\mathbb{Z}/3^{n+1}\mathbb{Z}) \equiv 2^{-a} (3 \text{Syrac}(\mathbb{Z}/3^n\mathbb{Z}) + 1) \pmod{3^{n+1}}, \quad a \sim \mathbf{Geom}(2),$$

with a independent of the level- n variable. Taking expectations directly in the characteristic function yields the equivalent recursion in dual space:

$$\psi_{n+1}(k) = \sum_{a=1}^{\infty} 2^{-a} \exp\left(-2\pi i \cdot \frac{2^{k-a} \bmod 3^{n+1}}{3^{n+1}}\right) \psi_n((k-a) \bmod 2 \cdot 3^{n-1}), \quad (4)$$

where the inner exponential is a 3^{n+1} -th root of unity at the integer $2^{k-a} \bmod 3^{n+1}$, well-defined for any integer $k-a$ since $\gcd(2, 3) = 1$. Equation (4) is the infinite-sum form: the geometric tail $\sum_{a=1}^{\infty} 2^{-a} = 1$ provides the correct normalisation directly.

We computed ψ_n for $n = 1, \dots, 21$ via two independent implementations:

1. Direct evaluation of (4) on the dual array of size $2 \cdot 3^{n-1}$. The sum over a is truncated at $a = 80$, after which the geometric weight $2^{-a} < 10^{-24}$ is below double-precision noise.
2. Independent verification at small n by direct evaluation of the level- $n+1$ recursion of P_n on the support of size 3^n , followed by discrete Fourier transform to obtain $\widehat{\text{Syrac}}_n$, then comparison with ψ_n . Both implementations agree to relative error $< 10^{-10}$ at every ξ and every $n \leq 8$ (the range over which the independent verification is run).

For $n \geq 17$, the dual array exceeds 1.7×10^8 complex entries and we computed in chunked passes. Up to $n = 19$, the computation runs on a laptop in a few hours. For $n = 20, 21$, we used a high-memory cloud instance with 961 GB of RAM. At $n = 21$, the dual array has $2 \cdot 3^{20} \approx 7.0 \times 10^9$ entries and occupies 112 GB as complex doubles; the auxiliary phase-factor array and the level-22 output array further dominate memory consumption. We did not compute $n = 22$: a single attempt during preparation of this paper failed because the working set exceeded available RAM during construction of the phase-factor array. Computing $n = 22$ in the present setup would require either a larger instance or restructured kernels.

A symmetry check is performed at each n : by the discussion in Section 2, $|\psi_n(k)|$ must equal $|\psi_n(k + 3^{n-1})|$. We sample 1000 values of k and verify this equality; the maximum observed discrepancy is below 10^{-20} at every n , consistent with floating-point round-off.

Source code, the underlying JSON data for Table 1, and verification scripts are available at the repository [3].

4 Discussion

The most striking feature of the data is the following. The simple closed-form predictor $\lfloor 4(n-1)/3 \rfloor$ matches $k^*(n)$ exactly for 14 consecutive values $n \in \{4, \dots, 17\}$, suggesting at first inspection a structural identity. The agreement then fails at $n = 18, 20, 21$, with the deviations $+1, +1, +2$. Yet the ratio $k^*(21)/21$ equals $4/3$ exactly, so the underlying linear behaviour with slope $4/3$ remains consistent with the data even after the floor formula fails. This dual pattern — exact agreement on a long initial segment, followed by deviations whose net effect leaves $k^*(21)/21$ at $4/3$ — is, on its face, a numerical curiosity rather than a structural identity.

The deviations at $n \in \{18, 20, 21\}$ are notable for being clustered in the upper portion of our range and for the unexpected $+2$ value at $n = 21$. The finite-range fit $M_n \sim n^{-2.1}$ over $9 \leq n \leq 21$ recorded in Remark 5 is consistent with Tao's super-polynomial upper bound, which permits a slowly increasing effective exponent.

Open questions

1. **Does $k^*(n)/n$ converge as $n \rightarrow \infty$, and is the limit $4/3$?** The available data are consistent with this, and at $n = 21$ we have $k^*(21)/21 = 4/3$ exactly, but a numerical observation on 18 data points cannot distinguish $4/3$ from a nearby limit such as $24/17$.

2. Identify the structural reason, if any, for the deviations at $n \in \{18, 20, 21\}$. The pair $(18, 20)$ shares a deviation of $+1$ and even parity, while 21 has odd parity and the unique deviation of $+2$; it is not clear whether these are coincidental, transient, or governed by a common arithmetic mechanism.
3. Determine whether the floor formula $\lfloor 4(n-1)/3 \rfloor$ is correct on density-one many n , density-zero many n , or something in between. Even with 14 consecutive agreements, the deviations $\{18, 20, 21\}$ in the last four values of our range provide no clear picture.
4. Determine the precise asymptotic exponent of decay of M_n , and whether the transition predicted by [1, Remark 1.15] (to $\exp(-cn)$) occurs at scales accessible to direct computation.
5. Extend the computation to $n \geq 22$.

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References

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